

A very high signal to noise spectrum towards μ -Col using UVES

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2017 ESO Calibration Workshop:
the second generation VLT instruments and friends

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UVES is a very friendly instrument :)

Talk outline

- A little bit about the high resolution spectrograph UVES.
- Some previous UVES high S/N work.
- Motivation for the current project.
- Choosing a target.
- The star mu-Col.
- Observations.
- Data reduction.
- Future work

UVES

- A high resolution cross-dispersed echelle spectrograph from around 300nm to 1100nm.
- Red and blue arms via dichroics. Red arm → FLAMES.
- Resolution 40,000 with a 1 arcsec slit, or up to 80,000 or 110,000 (blue/red) with narrow slits.
- In operation more than 15 years.
- Red CCD upgraded in 2009.

Previous UVES high S/N work

- Bhatt & Cami (2015) used archive data from the 346-nm setting of UVES ($\lambda=3050\text{-}3700$ Angstroms).
- They combined 371 spectra from **different** early-type stars (redened targets).
- Combined S/N ratio exceeded 1500 at a resolution of 58,000.
- They discovered 30 known interstellar features and 7 possible new lines.
- Part of their spectrum is shown below. See the Y-axis.

Motivation for the current project

- To see how high a S/N can we obtain with UVES for a single sightline.
- To use bad weather time on the VLT.

An finally (!) to find a target towards which we can do interesting science.

Choosing a star to observe

Plot the CaII interstellar column density from Gudennavar et al. (2012) against the stellar magnitude: plot (A).

Look for stars in The South (Dec < -24.6 degrees).

The star chosen is circled in red and has many UV lines detected (plots B and C, Hobbs 1999).

mu-Col (HD 38666)

An O9.5 star with $m_U=3.8$ and $m_V=5.2$.

Radial velocity around 109 km/s with Galactic latitude of -27 degrees.

→ Hence a runaway star (formation mechanisms).

Projected rotational velocity 111 km/s.

Hiparcos distance around 400-pc.

→ Hence a good object for the study of the nearby diffuse interstellar medium (stellar lines offset and smeared out), although IS lines are very weak.

Observations

- As this was a bad weather programme we used the Image Slicer#1 with opening aperture of 2.1x2.6" imaged on a 0.68" slit to achieve $R=60,000$.
- Many spectra were taken:

Setting	Wavelength Range (nm)	Exposure time (s)	Number of spectra
346nm	304-387	55	1294
437nm	374-499	40	367
580L nm	475-578	50	1232
580U nm	583-681	50	1232
860L nm	667-853	40	296
860U nm	865-1060	40	296

Raw Data (346nm)

Data reduction

- We used two versions of the UVES pipeline v4.4.8 and v5.7.0 with pixel flatfielding.
- Because this was an image slicer observation we used average extraction, no sky subtraction.
- To date the only non-standard thing we have done is to use 289 (normal) or 566 (Deuterium) flats for the 346nm setting and 1000 flats for the 437-nm setting. These were taken over a period of **+/- 90 days**. They were coadded in IRAF as the ESO UVES pipeline only accepts about 20 flatfields.
- UVES is one of the few instruments on Paranal that can calibrate with all the dome lights on.

Pending issues

No sky subtraction was performed. With Full Moon the ESO exposure time calculator predicts that the ratio of object to sky counts is around 10,000 at 350-nm to 100,000 at 650-nm. But still need to check position of absorption lines c.f. *molecfit*.

We have not yet taken into account any differences in the wavelength calibration due to temperature or pressure differences between day/night.

Effect of number of flatfields on S/N ratio achieved

As yet we have not tested the S/N ratio for this project as a function of number of flats used (time consuming to do with 1296 images).

However, we have done it for a 437-nm slit observation of HD 23180 from EDIBLES (Cox+).

Black: 5 flats
Green: 20 flats
Red: 100 flats
Blue: 220 flats

Estimating the S/N ratio for mu-Col

Increase in S/N as function of number of exposures for mu Col

Fit a 2nd order polynomial from 3851.0 to 3851.5 Angstroms for number of spectra=5,20,80,320 and 1296 for 346-nm setting.

There S/N increases from about 1000 with 5 exposures to nearly 10,000 with 1200 exposures. Hence we are not doing too badly (expect something like S/N=15,000).

Caveat is the “variability” in the S/N on different days.

Implication for calibration validity times

The calibration validity times for UVES are the following in days (service mode):

Blue_ECH	WAVE_ECH_BLUE	1.0
Blue_ECH	BIAS_BLUE	4.0
Blue_ECH	EFLAT_ECH_BLUE	2.0
Blue_ECH	FMTCHK_ECH_BLUE	3.0
Blue_ECH	ORDERDEF_ECH_BLUE	2.0

If we take calibrations outside of these windows then the observation may be resheduled.

Perhaps they could be relaxed for flatfields but for UVES no great gain in time and possible risk. Case by case basis c.f. FORS2 poster Boffin.

The future

We have been awarded time to repeat this on the cool ISM sightline towards Zeta Oph ($mB=2.58$) for which currently a UVES EDIBLES spectrum of S/N of “only” 800 exists.

Fig. 1 (a) HD 38666

Fig. 1 (b) HD 149757

Conclusions

It appears we can obtain a S/N perhaps between 5,000-10,000 per resolution element using UVES and the 346-nm setting.

Flatfields taken plus and minus 90 days away were used in the reduction to good effect. These should be carefully selected to avoid adding flats taken before and after interventions, earth tremors etc.

However, there are several items (sky subtraction, better wavelength calibration, optimal extraction?) that may be useful to improve the current spectrum.

Amin Fahring S/N ratio (preliminary)

Fig. 4. Comparison the S/N of HD 23180 with changing the number of flat frames. S/N ratios are the average of S/N measured at 5 different part of each central wavelength.

UVES pipeline version comparison

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